

Seedling News

March 1994

- ✓ Hybrid Pumpkins.
- ✓ Waterlogging and germination.
- ✓ Success with Onions.
- ✓ Precision seed sowing.

September 1993

- ✓ Ranunculus from seed.
- ✓ Vegetable growers co-operating.
- ✓ Seaweed for growth.

March 1993

- ✓ Flower fantasy.
- ✓ Palm Peat coir product.
- ✓ Plazdip aids in damping off control.

September 1992

- ✓ Flowers in Europe.
- ✓ Grass plugs at The Lost City.
- ✓ Pruning tunnel cucumbers.

March 1992

- ✓ Cabbage transplant treatments.
- ✓ Temperature and germination rate.
- ✓ Wattle seedling dieback.
- ✓ Water management in containers..

September 1991

- ✓ Primulas, a new force in gardens.
- ✓ Fungus gnats - not innocuous.
- ✓ Tunnel Talk - nutrition.
- ✓ Forestry seedling quality.
- ✓ Eelworm in vegetable crops.

March 1991

- ✓ Containerised tea cuttings.
- ✓ Tree roots - untangling the problems.
- ✓ Hybrid asparagus seedling transplants.
- ✓ Tunnel Talk - conductivity.

September 1990

- ✓ Root pruning with copper.
- ✓ Bayview - lawn grass plugs.
- ✓ Supersweet sweetcorn.

March 1990

- ✓ Containerised cane sugar plugs.
- ✓ Pansy varieties.
- ✓ Forestry transplant root structure.

September 1989

- ✓ Onion transplants as multi-seeded plugs.
- ✓ Lawn and pasture grasses as plug transplants.
- ✓ Club root of brassicas.

March 1989

- ✓ Accurate sowing of small seed by hand.
- ✓ Nutrient loading for better transplanting.
- ✓ Forestry plugs for early establishment.

September 1988

- ✓ Forestry transplants in cell trays – 10 years on
- ✓ Bedding plants.
- ✓ Transplanting techniques affect yield.
- ✓ Seed breeding - facing sanctions.

March 1988

- ✓ Bayview grass plugs for bowling green regeneration.
- ✓ Multi-seeded onion plugs.
- ✓ Using miniplugs.
- ✓ Pasture transplants.
- ✓ Single-eye sugar cane setts.

September 1987

- ✓ Food quality chain - seed to table.
- ✓ SGASA field day.
- ✓ Marketing view of choosing vegetable varieties.

March 1987

- ✓ Onion transplants as plugs.
- ✓ Composted pine bark as horticultural substrate.
- ✓ Clonal forestry.

November 1986

- ✓ Eucalyptus cuttings in containers.
- ✓ Kelpak - a seaweed growth stimulant.
- ✓ Starke Ayres vegetable research.

April 1985

- ✓ Containerised or bare root seedlings?.
- ✓ Sugar cane propagation.
- ✓ Containerised poplar cuttings.
- ✓ Pasture grass plugs.
- ✓ Speedling system in South Africa.

[Starke Ayres](#)